

0.5 mg indole acetic acid/liter, and 1 mg 2,4-D/liter while ER had 0.11 mg zeatin/liter, 2 mg 2,4-D/liter, and 0.07 mg picloram/liter.

Heat treatment increased callus induction efficiency in both media (see table). At 0 and 5 min, ER induced higher efficiencies than E10. At 15 min, however, there was a dramatic increase using E10 media. Cold shock, which has been a part of the standard operational

procedure in anther culture in most cereals, promotes the synchrony and viability of the pollen grains and may activate some enzymes which are necessary in callus production. On the other hand, heat treatment has been popular in *Brassica* genus. This study demonstrates that heat treatment before cold shock could increase callus production in IR42. In the same manner as in cold shock, heat may, aside from

promoting synchrony and viability, activate enzymes necessary to induce the pollen grains toward vegetative development (in this case, callus production) instead of their normal generative function.

Some of the calli produced have been transferred to plant regeneration medium to determine the plant regeneration efficiency after heat treatment. *J*

Pest Control and Management DISEASES

Seedling age in relation to sheath rot (ShR) occurrence in rice

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ShR caused by *Sarocladium oryzae* is

becoming an important disease in rainfed lowland rice, especially in delayed plantings. In 1984 wet season, ShR occurrence was observed in a replicated yield trial comprising 32 entries. Seedlings (25- and 50-d-old) were transplanted in 3 replications in 11-m² plots; 60 kg N/ha, 18 kg P/ha, and

17 kg K/ha were applied. N was used in 4 splits: 1/4 basal and the remaining as topdressing in 3 splits. Scoring followed the 1980 *Standard evaluation system for rice* at harvest under natural infection. The maximum score over three replications was recorded to avoid escapes.

ShR occurrence was high in 50-d-old seedlings. TCA72, TCA48, and TCA227 were highly resistant at both ages. CR1002, Jaishree, IR4819-17-3-2, and IET7591, which were resistant at 25 d were susceptible to highly susceptible when transplanted at 50 d (see table). TCA190-1, TCA148-3, TCA225, IR4570-74-2-2-3-3, RAU73-76-140-1, BR8, BR34, Janaki, and IET6286 were resistant to moderately resistant at both ages. In general, photoperiod-sensitive tall varieties were more resistant than photoperiod-insensitive ones. The mean score was 2.9 for 25d-old seedlings and 5.7 for 50-d-old. *J*

ShR score and other characters of 32 varieties.

Variety	ShR score ^a		Av days to 50% flowering	Photoperiod sensitivity ^b	Plant height ^c
	25 d	50 d			
RAUSBS80-565	1	5	124	S	9
RAUSBS 80-566	3	5	124	S	9
RAUSBS 80-571	1	5	121	S	9
TCA190-1	1	3	132	S	9
TCA72	1	1	115	S	9
TCA148-3	1	3	115	S	9
TCA80-4	1	5	115	I	5
TCA48	1	1	115	S	9
TCA225	1	3	122	S	9
TCA227	1	1	125	S	9
RAUSBS 80-585	5	9	124	S	9
RP1491-24	5	9	122	I	1
RAU83-18-8	1	5	116	I	1
R114-2-1-1-1	9	9	128	I	1
IR4570-74-2-2-3-3	1	5	108	I	1
MTU7029 (Swarna)	7	9	122	I	1
RAU73-16-1-40-1	1	3	112	I	1
CR1002	1	9	119	I	1
RAU83-8-4	5	5	111	I	1
Pankaj	5	9	121	I	1
BR8	1	3	117	S	9
Jaishree	1	9	120	I	9
Mahsuri	3	5	115	I	9
Radha	5	9	115	I	5
BR34	3	3	108	S	9
Janki (64-117)	1	3	114	S	9
IR4819-17-3-2	3	9	112	I	1
CR1009 (Savitri)	9	9	102	I	1
ET759 1	1	7	123	I	1
IET6286	1	3	115	I	5
IR13146-45-2-3	7	9	115	I	1
RP975-109-2	5	9	120	I	1
Mean	2.9	5.7			

^aBy SES. ^bS = photoperiod sensitive, I = photoperiod insensitive. ^c1 = semidwarf, 5 = intermediate, 9 = tall.

Rice grassy stunt (GSV) and rice ragged stunt (RSV) carriers

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ELISA tests on brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* collected daily in a high-beam light trap on the top of a three-floor building at IRRI were conducted to identify GSV and RSV carriers. The light trap was designed to catch migrating BPH.

Individual BPH were homogenized with 0.50 ml-0.02 M phosphate buffer

GSV and RSV carriers in BPH caught in a high-beam light trap, IRRI, 1983–84.

Collection dates	BPH tested no.	GSV carrier		RSV carrier		Collection dates	BPH tested no.	GSV carrier		RSV carrier	
		no.	%	no.	%			no.	%	no.	%
28 Jan-6 Feb	5	0	—	1	20.0	5-14 Sep	199	1	0.5	2	1.0
7-16 Feb	0	—	—	—	—	15-24 Sep	145	0	—	0	—
17-26 Feb	13	1	7.7	2	15.4	25 Sep-4 Oct	55	0	—	0	—
27 Feb-8 Mar	67	8	11.9	13	19.4	5-14 Oct	43	0	—	0	—
9-18 Mar	33	1	3.0	0	—	15-24 Oct	77	1	1.3	0	—
19-28 Mar	207	0	—	0	—	25 Oct-3 Nov	92	0	—	0	—
29 Mar-7 Apr	271	9	3.3	34	12.5	4-13 Nov	4	1	25.0	0	—
8-17 Apr	134	0	—	3	2.2	14-23 Nov	109	0	—	0	—
18-27 Apr	139	0	—	4	2.9	24 Nov-3 Dec	45	0	—	1	2.2
28 Apr-7 May	74	1	1.4	2	2.7	4-13 Dec	0	—	—	—	—
8-17 May	50	2	3.3	1	1.7	14-23 Dec	0	—	—	—	—
18-27 May	65	1	1.5	3	4.6	24 Dec-3 Jan 1984	0	—	—	—	—
28 May-6 Jun	27	0	—	3	11.1	4-13 Jan	2	—	—	—	—
7-16 Jun	99	3	3.0	6	6.1	14-23 Jan	2	—	—	—	—
17-26 Jun	91	1	1.1	3	3.3	24 Jan-2 Feb	0	—	—	—	—
27 Jun-6 Jul	108	0	—	4	3.7	3-12 Feb	8	—	—	—	—
7-16 Jul	41	0	—	2	4.9	13-22 Feb	3	—	—	—	—
17-26 Jul	0	—	—	—	—	23 Feb-3 Mar	2	—	—	—	—
27 Jul-5 Aug	0	—	—	—	—	4-13 Mar	147	1	0.7	3	2.0
6-15 Aug	0	—	—	—	—	14-23 Mar	431	21	4.9	4	0.9
16-25 Aug	339	3	0.9	7	2.1	24 Mar-2 Apr	399	0	—	3	0.8
26 Aug-4 Sep	407	0	—	17	4.2	Total or average	3943	55	1.4	118	3.0

Percentage GSV and RSV carriers among migrating BPH from daily catches in a high-beam light trap at IRRI, 1983–84.

(pH 6.5) containing 0.15 M NaCl, 0.05% Tween 20, 0.02% NaN₃ and 2% polyvinylpyrrolidone. The homogenate was separately tested in ELISA using a purified immunoglobulin against GSV and RSV.

Of 3,943 BPH tested from Jan 1983 to Mar 1984, 1.4% carried GSV, 3.0% carried RSV, and 0.3% carried both viruses. Carriers per 10-d catch varied from 0.5 to 25.0% for GSV and from 0.8

to 20.0% for RSV (see table). Large numbers of BPH were trapped in Mar–Jun and Aug–Nov (see figure). *IR*

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Effect of foliar spray of macro- and micronutrients on sheath rot (ShR) incidence and rice grain yield

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ShR caused by *Sarocladium oryzae* is found in most rice-growing areas in